

C omparison of stretching exercises and leg massage on the severity of restless legs syndrome for hemodialysis patients

Comparación de ejercicios de estiramiento y masajes de piernas sobre la gravedad del síndrome de piernas inquietas en pacientes en hemodiálisis

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Abstract

Background: Restless legs syndrome is a neurologic condition resulting in an irresistible urge to move legs. Restless legs syndrome affects sleep quality and can cause daytime sleepiness, low energy, irritability, and depression. Lifestyle changes such as doing regular daily stretching exercises and leg massage may reduce the severity of the syndrome.

Methods: A quasi-experimental design was used to conduct a study that started on October 2022 on 90 hemodialysis patients in hemodialysis centers in Wasit and Thi-Qar to compare the effectiveness of stretching exercises and massage on the severity of restless legs syndrome among hemodialysis patients using the International Restless Legs Syndrome Study Group rating scale. Data were analyzed using Friedman, Kruskal Wallis, and Mann-Whitney U Test with IBM's Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) statistic software.

Results: The study found there was a significant difference in the severity of restless legs syndrome when comparing the severity before the interventions, at the end of the first week, and at the end of the second week ($P\text{-value} < 0.001$) among both the stretching exercises and leg massage groups.

Conclusion: stretching exercises and massage were effective in decreasing the severity of restless legs syndrome, with stretching exercises being more effective.

Keywords: Stretching Exercises, Leg Massage, Restless Legs Syndrome, Hemodialysis Patients

Resumen

Antecedentes: el síndrome de piernas inquietas es una afección neurológica que provoca una necesidad irresistible de mover las piernas. El síndrome de piernas inquietas afecta la calidad del sueño y puede provocar somnolencia diurna, falta de energía, irritabilidad y depresión. Los cambios en el estilo de vida, como hacer ejercicios de estiramiento diarios con regularidad y masajes en las piernas, pueden reducir la gravedad del síndrome.

Métodos: Se utilizó un diseño cuasiexperimental para realizar un estudio que comenzó en octubre de 2022 en 90 pacientes en hemodiálisis en centros de hemodiálisis en Wasit y Thi-Qar para comparar la efectividad de los ejercicios de estiramiento y masajes sobre la gravedad del síndrome de piernas inquietas entre pacientes en hemodiálisis, utilizando la escala de calificación del Grupo Internacional de Estudio del Síndrome de Piernas Inquietas. Los datos se analizaron utilizando la prueba U de Friedman, Kruskal Wallis y Mann-Whitney con el software estadístico Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) de IBM.

Resultados: El estudio encontró que hubo una diferencia significativa en la gravedad del síndrome de piernas inquietas al comparar la gravedad antes de las intervenciones, al final de la primera semana y al final de la segunda semana (valor $P = < 0,001$) entre tanto en el grupo de ejercicios de estiramiento como en el de masaje de piernas.

Conclusión: los ejercicios de estiramiento y masajes fueron efectivos para disminuir la gravedad del síndrome de piernas inquietas, siendo más efectivos los ejercicios de estiramiento.

Palabras clave: Ejercicios de estiramiento, Masaje de piernas, Síndrome de piernas inquietas, Pacientes en hemodiálisis

Hemodialysis is necessary for patients with end-stage kidney disease to survive until a kidney donation is possible for them¹.

Restless legs syndrome is a condition that hemodialysis patients frequently experience^{2,3}. In order to alleviate a subjectively distressing sensation that is usually characterized as creeping, crawling, tingling, or painful, a person with restless legs syndrome (RLS) has the urge to move their legs^{4,5}.

Older persons are more likely to have RLS⁶. This might be because older persons engage in fewer physical activities⁷. Adults who lead sedentary lifestyles and lack physical activity are susceptible to falls and developing RLS^{8,9}. Unfortunately, research has shown that patients from Iraq have poor views on leading healthy lifestyles and engaging in little physical activity^{10,11}. RLS susceptibility is elevated by certain factors, including smoking, obesity, with women being more prone since marital status has a big impact on women's weight, and poor physical activity¹²⁻¹⁴. RLS may result in serious problems with sleeping, poor sleep quality, problems with the ability to do daily activities, and a higher risk of cardiovascular, as RLS has been found to be common among patients with hypertension and hypertension is a risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, also RLS may lead to cerebral disease¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

The pathophysiology of RLS implies that the majority of RLS patients have a localized iron deficit in their brains, despite having normal peripheral levels of iron, and it has been acknowledged that patients on hemodialysis frequently have iron deficiency anemia^{19,20}. The current prevalent hypothesis states that brain iron insufficiency is a significant biological factor that contributes to RLS and is typically brought on by a number of factors, such as low peripheral iron and/or genetics²¹.

RLS lowers patients' quality of life since it has negative effects on their mental and physical health. It has been connected to restless nights, daytime sleepiness, and a greater likelihood of sedative-hypnotic use²². The significant prevalence of RLS in hemodialysis patients and its adverse effects on the patient's quality of life call for increasing awareness of RLS treatment options²³. Since it has been found that more than half of hemodialysis patients in Iraq don't have adequate income, have morbidities and hindered medication elimination, and many pharmaceutical therapies of RLS have been linked to a number of side effects, like nausea and the worsening of symptoms, an economic non-pharmacologic interventions, like stretching exercises, changing the patient's dialysis modalities, and the massage that doesn't require a lot of physical activity but increases the release of dopamine, are safer than pharmaceutical therapy and effective in managing RLS^{11,24-30}.

Stretching exercises and massage therapy are two complementary therapeutic modalities with several beneficial effects that have been demonstrated in previous studies^{27,29,31,32}. However, comparing the effectiveness of stretching exercises and leg massage on the severity of RLS has not yet been studied in previous studies, which is the current study's main goal.

Study Design

The researcher used a quasi-experimental design

Setting of the study

Wasit Directorate which are Martyr Fairouz Hospital and Al-Zahra Teaching Hospital, and in the hemodialysis centers available in Thi-Qar Directorate which are Al-Hussein Teaching Hospital, Al-Refaai General Hospital, and Al-Nasiriya General Hospital

Sample Size

The researcher used a purposive sampling method to select restless legs syndrome patients from hemodialysis centers. The sample size calculation formula indicated that 25 patients were required for each of the three study groups.

Ethical Consideration

Approval taken from the Nursing College Council of the University of Baghdad was obtained for the study protocol prior to data collection.

Data collection tool

The current study used the International Restless Legs Syndrome Study Group rating scale which is a commonly used scale for assessing the severity of restless legs syndrome³⁵. The researcher used the Arabic-validated version of the scale³⁶. The instrument is measured and assessed based on a five-level Likert rating scale.

Construction of the Stretching Exercises and Leg Massage Programs

A- Construction of the Stretching Exercises:

The preliminary (need) assessment findings from the patients served as the basis for the creation of the stretching exercises program, along with knowledge gleaned from a review of pertinent scientific literature and previous studies^{31,32,37-39}.

B- Conducting Stretching Exercises

The program was approved by a physical therapist and then conducted on hemodialysis patients with restless legs syndrome. The program is composed of three phases implemented after allocating patients randomly into one of the three groups (stretching exercises, leg massage, and control group)

Results

Construction of the Leg Massage Program:

The preliminary (need) assessment findings from the patients served as the basis for the creation of the Leg massage program, along with knowledge gleaned from a review of pertinent scientific literature, as well as based on previous studies^{27,40-42}.

Statistical Data Analysis

The researcher used the SPSS application (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version (24) to enter and analyze the collected data as well as Microsoft Excel Program (2016).

Table 1 shows there is a significant difference within the stretching exercises group in response to the RLS severity when comparing the severity of RLS during the pre-test, at the end of the first week, and at the end of the second week (P-value = <0.001). Table 1 shows there is a significant difference within the leg massage group in response to the RLS severity when comparing the severity of RLS during the pre-test, at the end of the first week, and at the end of the second week (P-value = <0.001). Table 1 shows there is no significant difference among the control group when comparing the severity of RLS during the pre-test, at the end of the first week, and at the end of the second week (P-value = 0.070).

Table 1 shows there is a significant difference among the stretching exercises group, leg massage group, and control group in response to the severity of RLS at the end of the first week (P-value=0.015). Table 1 shows there is a significant difference among the stretching exercises group, leg massage group, and control group in response to the severity of RLS at the end of the second week (P-value=<0.001).

Table 2 shows there is no significant difference between the leg massage group and the control group in response to the severity of RLS during the pre-test period (P-value =0.982). Table 2 shows there is no significant difference between the stretching exercises group and the leg massage group in response to the severity of RLS at the end of the first week of the interventions (P-value =0.266). Table 2 shows there is a significant difference between the stretching exercises group and the control group in response to the severity of RLS, at the end of the first week (P-value =0.013). Table 2 shows there is a significant difference between the leg massage group and the control group in response to the severity of RLS at the end of the first week (P-value =0.019). Table 2 shows there is a significant difference in response to the severity of RLS between the stretching exercises group and the leg massage group at the end of the second week (P-value =0.048). Table 2 shows there is a significant difference between the stretching exercises group and the control group in response to the severity of RLS at the end of the second week (P-value =<0.001). Table (2) shows there is a significant difference between the leg massage group and the control group in response to the severity of RLS at the end of the second week (P-value =0.001).

Table 1. The statistical difference within the same group and among the groups in response to the severity of restless legs syndrome

Time of Assessment	Stretching Exercises Group		Leg Massage Group		Control Group		Kruskal-Wallis Test	P-value
	Mean &R	MR	M&R	MR	M&R	MR		
Pre-Test	21.97 & 3	45.28	21.53 & 3	45.78	21.83 & 2.15	45.43	0.006	0.997
At the end of the first week	17.53 & 2	37.47	17.93 & 1.93	42.72	21.57 & 1.93	56.32	8.410	0.015
At the end of the second week	12.03 & 1	29.77	14.47 & 1.07	42.50	21.47 & 1.92	64.23	27.605	<0.001
Friedman Test	60		58.207		5.304			
P-value	<0.001		<0.001		0.070			

M&R mean and mean rank, MR mean rank

Table 2. Comparison among stretching exercises, leg massage, and the control groups concerning the severity of restless leg syndrome throughout the study period

Time of Assessment	Group (A) Mean Rank	Group (B) Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U Test	P-value
Pre-Test	Stretching 30.27	Massage 30.73	443	0.916
	Stretching 30.52	Control 30.48	449.500	0.994
	Massage 30.55	Control 30.45	448.500	0.982
At the End of the First Week	Stretching 28.03	Massage 32.97	376	0.266
	Stretching 24.93	Control 36.07	283	0.013
	Massage 25.25	Control 35.75	292.500	0.019
At the End of the Second Week	Stretching 26.20	Massage 34.80	321	0.048
	Stretching 19.07	Control 41.93	107	<0.001
	Massage 23.20	Control 37.80	231	0.001

The findings of this study indicated that there is a significant difference when comparing the severity of restless legs syndrome during the pre-test, at the end of the first week, and at the end of the second week of stretching exercises (P -value ≤ 0.001), which means the stretching exercises were effective in decreasing the severity of RLS.

RLS was discovered to be connected to oxidative stress and chronic inflammation in uremic individuals⁴³. As dopamine regeneration is an intracellular enzymatic process that requires iron as a cofactor, then inadequate levels of iron in the central nervous system may lead to secondary RLS⁴⁴.

Low levels of adenosine would induce hyperarousal and enhanced activation of the limbs while also triggering other pathways linked to RLS, such as the dopaminergic and hypoxic systems, as adenosine is an antagonist of ascending arousal systems⁴⁵. The brain's levels of serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine are increased by exercise, just like what can drugs do. In addition, neurotransmitter balances are enhanced and better regulated by exercise, which eventually contributes to mental wellness⁴⁶. An Indian study in 2016 supports the current study findings as they found there was a significant difference (P -value $= 0.001$) among the stretching exercises group when comparing the mean scores during the pre-test, at the end of the first week, and at the end of the second week (23.95, 15.74, 10.44) respectively, indicating that stretching exercises were effective in reducing the severity of RLS⁴⁷.

The findings of the study indicated that there is a significant difference (P -value ≤ 0.001) when comparing the severity of RLS during the pre-test, at the end of the first week, and at the end of the second week of leg massage which means the leg massage was effective in decreasing the severity of RLS.

Dopamine, which is behind the pleasure and relaxation sensations, is released more readily during a massage⁴⁸. A study showed that massage therapy is effective at enhancing end-stage renal disease patients' quality of life and sleep, and they advise using this technique as a non-invasive sleep problem treatment⁴⁹.

A study in Iran (41) supports the current study findings as they found there is a significant difference (P -value ≤ 0.001) when comparing the mean rank of the Swedish massage group during the pre-test, immediately after the massage and one month after the massage (20.03, 14.60, 19.63) respectively, which means that the massage was effective in decreasing the severity of RLS.

The findings of the study indicated that there was a significant difference (P -value $= 0.013$) when comparing stretching exercises and the control groups' mean rank scores, also there was a significant difference (P -value ≤ 0.001) when comparing stretching exercises and the control groups' mean rank scores at the end of the second week, which means that stretching exercises were effective in decreasing the severity of restless legs syndrome.

The findings of the study indicated that at the end of the second week, there was a significant difference (P -value $= 0.048$) when comparing the stretching exercises and the leg massage groups' mean rank scores (26.20, 34.80) respectively for the advantage of the stretching exercises group who owned the lowest mean rank score, which means that stretching exercises were more effective than leg massage in decreasing the severity of restless legs syndrome. The results weren't unexpected to the researcher since RLS symptoms worsen during periods of inactivity or resting, the relief of symptoms following exercise activity could be interpreted in relation to the fact that engaging in exercise increases cardiac output and blood flow, decreasing peripheral hypoxia in muscles and thus relieving RLS symptoms. Exercise also promotes the release of dopamine and endorphins, which have analgesic effects⁵⁰.

The findings of the study indicated that at the end of the first week, there was a significant difference (P -value $= 0.019$) when comparing leg massage and the control groups' mean rank scores, which means that leg massage was effective in decreasing the severity of RLS, also there was a significant difference (P -value $= 0.001$) when comparing between the leg massage and the control groups mean rank scores at the end of the second week, which means that leg massage was effective in decreasing the severity of RLS. A study in Iran supports the current study findings as they found there was a non-significant difference (P -value $= 0.64$) when comparing the Swedish massage and the control groups' mean rank scores before the interventions. However, there was a significant difference (P -value $= 0.003$) when comparing the Swedish massage and the control groups' mean rank scores immediately after the intervention, which indicates that the Swedish massage was effective in decreasing the severity of RLS. However, after one month, there was no significant difference (P -value $= 0.74$) when comparing the Swedish massage and the control groups' mean rank scores⁴¹.

The study findings showed that both stretching exercises and leg massage alleviate the severity of RLS for hemodialysis patients, with stretching exercises being more effective than leg massage in alleviating the severity of RLS.

Recommendations

Nurses should be encouraged to implement structured, approved-by-specialist stretching exercises and leg massage programs to reduce the severity of restless legs syndrome for hemodialysis patients. Future studies with longer follow-up duration, larger sample sizes, and a randomized sample collection method are required.

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Conflict of interest

All authors have no conflict of interest related to this study.

References

- Lin XW, Zhang JF, Qiu MY, Ni LY, Yu HL, Kuo SH, Ondo WG, Yu Q, Wu YC. Restless legs syndrome in end stage renal disease patients undergoing hemodialysis. *BMC neurology*. 2019 Dec;19:1-7.
- Scherer JS, Combs SA, Brennan F. Sleep disorders, restless legs syndrome, and uremic pruritus: diagnosis and treatment of common symptoms in dialysis patients. *American Journal of Kidney Diseases*. 2017 Jan 1;69(1):117-128.
- Hussein MR, Makki HM. Neurological Assessment of Hemodialysis Patients a Single Center Study. *International Journal of Medicine and Pharmaceutical Science (IJMPS)*. 2018 Apr;8:57-74.
- Walters AS, Aldrich MS, Allen R, Ancoli-Israel S, Buchholz D, Chokroverty S, Coccagna G, Earley C, Ehrenberg B, Feest TG, Hening W. Toward a better definition of the restless legs syndrome. *Movement disorders: official journal of the Movement Disorder Society*. 1995 Sep;10(5):634-642.
- Ekbom KA. Restless legs syndrome. *Neurology*. 1960 Sep 1;10(9):868.
- Al-Hussainy SI, Hatem AK. The Prevalence of Restless Leg Syndrome in Iraqi Multiple Sclerosis Patients. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*. 2018 Jun 1;9(6).
- AlAbedi GA, Najji AB. Impact of physical activity program upon elderly quality of life at Al-Amara city/Iraq. *Medico Legal Update*. Prof. (Dr) RK Sharma. 2020 Jul;20(3):6.
- Hassan SK, Tawfeeq WA. Risk and Fear of Falling among Old People (A Sample from Baghdad City). *Turkish journal of physiotherapy and rehabilitation*. 2021 April;32(3): 14874- 14882.
- Mousa AM, Mansour K. Effectiveness of an Instructional Program Concerning Healthy Lifestyle on Patients' Attitudes after Percutaneous Coronary Intervention at Cardiac Centers in Baghdad City. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*. 2020 Jun 30;33(1):1-1.
- Abdul-hussain M. Effectiveness of an Instructional Program Concerning Non-Pharmacological Guideline on Controlling Essential Hypertension among Patients at AL-Sader Hospital in AL-Najaf AL-Ashraf City. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*. 2020 Sep 27;33(1):93-103.
- Hussein M, Ahmed S. Effectiveness of an Educational Program on Patients' Knowledge Concerning care of Vascular Access of Hemodialysis in Al-Muthana Teaching Hospitals. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*. 2020 Sep 27;33(1):33-43.
- Batool-Anwar S, Li Y, De Vito K, Malhotra A, Winkelman J, Gao X. Lifestyle factors and risk of restless legs syndrome: prospective cohort study. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2016 Feb 15;12(2):187-194.
- Lin S, Zhang H, Gao T, Zhong F, Sun Y, Cai J, Ma A. The association between obesity and restless legs syndrome: a systemic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *Journal of affective disorders*. 2018 Aug 1;235:384-391.
- Jasim HM, Hussein HM, Al-Kaseer EA. Obesity among females in Al-Sader city Baghdad, Iraq, 2017. *Journal of the Faculty of Medicine Baghdad*. 2018 Sep 2;60(2):105-107.
- Gao X, Ba DM, Bagai K, Liu G, Ma C, Walters AS. Treating Restless Legs Syndrome Was Associated With Low Risk of Cardiovascular Disease: A Cohort Study With 3.4 Years of Follow-Up. *Journal of the American Heart Association*. 2021 Feb 16;10(4):e018674.
- McDermott M, Brown DL, Chervin RD. Sleep disorders and the risk of stroke. *Expert review of neurotherapeutics*. 2018 Jul 3;18(7):523-531.
- Khasal QA, Jabbar DK, Shinjar FJ. Risk factors for Cardiovascular Diseases among Diabetic Patients attending Al Nasiriya Diabetic and Endocrinology Center. Jinu. M, Thankamma. P. George, NA Balaram, Sujisha. SS 2. Profile of Burn Deaths: A Study Based on Postmortem Examination of Burn Cases at RNT. 2020 Jul;20(3):585.
- Liu Y, Liu G, Li L, Yang J, Ma S. Evaluation of cardiovascular risk factors and restless legs syndrome in women and men: a preliminary population-based study in China. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2018 Mar 15;14(3):445-450.
- Ali A, Salih RM. Renal anemia syndromes in iraqi hemodialysis patients according to iron status. *Saudi Journal of Kidney Diseases and Transplantation*. 2018 Jan 1;29(1):127-135.
- Allen RP. Restless leg syndrome/Willis-Ekbom disease pathophysiology. *Sleep medicine clinics*. 2015 Sep 1;10(3):207-214.
- Connor JR, Patton SM, Oexle K, Allen RP. Iron and restless legs syndrome: treatment, genetics and pathophysiology. *Sleep medicine*. 2017 Mar 1;31:61-70.
- Turk AC, Ozkurt S, Turgal E, Sahin F. The association between the prevalence of restless leg syndrome, fatigue, and sleep quality in patients undergoing hemodialysis. *Saudi medical journal*. 2018 Aug;39(8):792.
- Kutlu R, Selcuk NY, Sayin S, Kal O. Restless legs syndrome and quality of life in chronic hemodialysis patients. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*. 2018;21(5):573-577.
- Garcia-Borreguero D, Benitez A, Kohonen R, Allen R. Augmentation of restless leg syndrome (Willis-Ekbom disease) during long-term dopaminergic treatment. *Postgraduate medicine*. 2015 Nov

- 4;127(7):716-25.
25. Fritz S. *The scientific art of therapeutic massage. Fundamentals of Therapeutic Massage*, third ed. Mosby Inc., St. Louis. 2004:125-153.
 26. Gnatta JR, Kurebayashi LF, Turrini RN, Silva MJ. Aromaterapia e enfermagem: concepção histórico-teórica. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da USP*. 2016;50:127-133.
 27. Nasiri M, Abbasi M, Khosroabadi ZY, Saghafi H, Hamzeei F, Amiri MH, Yusefi H. Short-term effects of massage with olive oil on the severity of uremic restless legs syndrome: a double-blind placebo-controlled trial. *Complementary therapies in medicine*. 2019 Jun 1;44:261-268.
 28. Kennedy C, Ryan SA, Kane T, Costello RW, Conlon PJ. The impact of change of renal replacement therapy modality on sleep quality in patients with end-stage renal disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of nephrology*. 2018 Feb;31:61-70.
 29. Shahgholian N, Jazi SK, Karimian J, Valiani M. The effects of two methods of reflexology and stretching exercises on the severity of restless leg syndrome among hemodialysis patients. *Iranian journal of nursing and midwifery research*. 2016 May;21(3):219.
 30. Schwab RJ. *Periodic limb movement disorder (PLMD) and restless legs syndrome (RLS)*. MSD Manuals. 2022.
 31. Algendy AA, Bahgat ZF. Effect of Muscles Stretching Exercises on Severity of Restless Legs Syndrome of Adult Patients Undergoing Hemodialysis. *Journal of Health, Medicine and Nursing*. 2019;68:76-88.
 32. Fauzi A, Triaswati R. The effect of intradialytic stretching training on restless legs syndrome and sleep quality in hemodialysis patients. *Korean Journal of Adult Nursing*. 2021 Feb 1;33(1):37-43.
 33. Emamverdi M, Mohammadpour A, Badiie Aval S, Sajjadi M. Comparing the effects of reflexology massage and acupressure on the quality of sleep in hemodialysis patients: A randomized clinical trial. *Journal of Mazandaran University of Medical Sciences*. 2019 Sep 10;29(176):34-46.
 34. Allen RP, Picchietti DL, Garcia-Borreguero D, Ondo WG, Walters AS, Winkelman JW, Zucconi M, Ferri R, Trenkwalder C, Lee HB, International Restless Legs Syndrome Study Group. Restless legs syndrome/Willis-Ekbom disease diagnostic criteria: updated International Restless Legs Syndrome Study Group (IRLSSG) consensus criteria—history, rationale, description, and significance. *Sleep medicine*. 2014 Aug 1;15(8):860-873.
 35. Allen RP, Kushida CA, Atkinson MJ, RLS QoL Consortium. Factor analysis of the International Restless Legs Syndrome Study Group's scale for restless legs severity. *Sleep medicine*. 2003 Mar 1;4(2):133-135.
 36. Shalash AS, Elrassas HH, Monzem MM, Salem HH, Moneim AA, Moustafa RR. Restless legs syndrome in Egyptian medical students using a validated Arabic version of the Restless Legs Syndrome Rating Scale. *Sleep Medicine*. 2015 Dec 1;16(12):1528-1531.
 37. Zirak Aliabadi A, Mirhosseini Z, Rastaghi S, Rad M. Comparison of the effect of cold dialysate versus stretching exercises on severity of restless legs syndrome in patients undergoing hemodialysis: a randomized controlled trial. *Evidence Based Care*. 2020 Oct 1;10(3):15-22.
 38. Aliasgharpour M, Abbasi Z, Razi SP, Kazemnezhad A. The effect of stretching exercises on severity of restless legs syndrome in patients on hemodialysis. *Asian journal of sports medicine*. 2016 Jun;7(2).
 39. Shamekh AH, Hassan NZ, Rashwan ZI, Fathalla NF. Effect of stretching exercises versus thermotherapy on restless legs syndrome symptoms, pain, and quality of sleep among pregnant women. *International Journal of Health Sciences*. 2022;6(S6):11204-11220.
 40. Azimpour S, Hosseini HS, Eftekhari A, Kazemi M. The effects of vibration and massage on severity of symptoms of restless leg syndrome and sleep quality in hemodialysis patients; a randomized cross-over clinical trial. *Journal of Renal Injury Prevention*. 2018 Dec 14;8(2):106-111.
 41. Ghanbari A, Shahrabaki PM, Dehghan M, Mardanparvar H, Abadi EK, Emami A, Sarikhani-Khorrami E. Comparison of the effect of reflexology and Swedish massage on restless legs syndrome and sleep quality in patients undergoing hemodialysis: a randomized clinical trial. *International Journal of Therapeutic Massage & Bodywork*. 2022 Jun;15(2):1.
 42. Hashemi SH, Hajbagheri A, Aghajani M. The effect of massage with lavender oil on restless leg syndrome in hemodialysis patients: a randomized controlled trial. *Nursing and midwifery studies*. 2015 Dec;4(4).
 43. Higuchi T, Abe M, Mizuno M, Yamazaki T, Suzuki H, Moriuchi M, Oikawa O, Okawa E, Ando H, Okada K. Association of restless legs syndrome with oxidative stress and inflammation in patients undergoing hemodialysis. *Sleep medicine*. 2015 Aug 1;16(8):941-948.
 44. Einollahi B, Izadianmehr N. Restless leg syndrome: a neglected diagnosis. *Nephro-urology monthly*. 2014 Sep;6(5).
 45. Earley CJ, Uhl GR, Clemens S, Ferré S. Connectome and molecular pharmacological differences in the dopaminergic system in restless legs syndrome (RLS): plastic changes and neuroadaptations that may contribute to augmentation. *Sleep medicine*. 2017 Mar 1;31:71-77.
 46. Kaiser Permanente. *Regular exercise benefits both mind and body: a psychiatrist explains*. 2021.
 47. Kaur J, Venkatesan M, Kaur H, Rawat P, Massey H. Effectiveness of muscle stretching exercise on restless leg syndrome among patients undergoing haemodialysis. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2016 Jun;2164-2169.
 48. Moyer CA, Rounds J, Hannum JW. A meta-analysis of massage therapy research. *Psychological bulletin*. 2004 Jan;130(1):3.
 49. Malekshahi F, Aryamanesh F, Fallahi S. The effects of massage therapy on sleep quality of patients with end-stage renal disease undergoing hemodialysis. *Sleep and Hypnosis*. 2018;20:91-95.
 50. Akbaş P, Yaman Sözbir Ş. Non-pharmacological methods used in coping with restless leg syndrome (RLS): a systematic review. *Sleep and Biological Rhythms*. 2021 Jul;19(3):215-225.